

The Cascade Outreach Model in astronomy engagement during National Science Week

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The “Cascade Outreach Model in Astronomy Engagement” project, implemented during National Science Week 2023 in South Africa, was a collaborative initiative designed to ignite curiosity and foster a passion for astronomy among diverse communities, particularly the youth. The project also highlighted potential career paths in STEM fields. Through strategic partnerships with local education departments and the active involvement of dedicated outreach ambassadors – mostly astronomy postgraduate students – the initiative expanded its reach across six of South Africa’s nine provinces.

A key innovation of the project was introducing the “cascade outreach” model, first developed by the Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy (*IDIA, n.d.*), inspired by the work of Dr Carolina Ödman-Govender. This model was crucial in disseminating astronomical knowledge while promoting diversity, inclusivity, and leadership skills in science communication. The project trained a new group of science communicators from diverse backgrounds, ensuring that astronomy outreach efforts were relatable and accessible to all.

The project had a significant reach, particularly by targeting learners in remote areas such as townships and rural communities. These locations are often underserved by similar initiatives due to logistical challenges, including their distance from urban centres, airports, and other transportation networks. By overcoming these barriers, the project successfully extended opportunities to learners and communities that are typically excluded from such programs, thereby introducing the wonders of astronomy to individuals who may not have had prior exposure to such educational experiences. According to participants’ feedback, the engagements were informative and deeply inspiring, as they had the chance to interact with ambassadors who shared similar life experiences. This personalised approach made astronomy more accessible, tangible and relevant to their lives, sparking curiosity and encouraging them to aspire to great things.

Moreover, the project had a positive effect on the ambassadors themselves. By

providing them with hands-on experience in science communication and outreach, the initiative provided them with an opportunity to learn valuable skills in communication. This led to the creation of a supportive network of science communicators, fostering ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Introduction

In today’s interconnected world, effective science communication is pivotal in promoting public understanding, support, and engagement in scientific endeavours. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the landscape of public science communication varies across countries and is shaped by diverse socioeconomic, historical, cultural, and political factors (*Joubert, 2018; Manzini, 2003; Trench et al., 2014*). By recognising and analysing these influences, we can develop a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and barriers the South African public faces in their interactions with science.

Addressing these barriers is paramount in South Africa, given the socio-economic issues such as poverty and unemployment that significantly impact the reception of science within communities.

To enhance public engagement with science, mobilising a collective of advocates is essential. By pushing boundaries, going beyond the ordinary, and actively seeking solutions, we can bridge the gap between science and

society, empowering communities along the way. It is vital to move beyond traditional outreach methods that focus solely on outreach for its own sake or rely on a one-size-fits-all approach to make a meaningful impact. Instead, we must prioritise inclusion, relatability, and cultural sensitivity when engaging with different audiences. This is precisely what the Cascade Outreach Model seeks to address. The model also empowers young scientists by equipping them with the opportunities and skills necessary to communicate science and astronomy effectively to the public. Simply giving a talk and sending the same team to cover diverse regions is not enough. It is important to tailor outreach engagements to the unique needs of each community.

Challenges in public engagement with science and astronomy

The first step in achieving this transformative change is to delve into the root causes and comprehend the barriers to public engagement with science. Only by doing so can we facilitate meaningful progress, as our efforts will be based on a profound understanding of the landscape of science, science communication, and the people of South Africa.

Access to new knowledge

Access to new knowledge is closely tied to education levels, and individuals in marginalised communities may face significant barriers to accessing such knowledge (see Figure 1). One of these barriers is the limited availability of resources and infrastructure, particularly in rural areas like some communities in South Africa.

Figure 1: Percentage of youth per province that cited lack of money as the reason for not attending any educational institution in 2017 (South African Market Insights, 2023)

Guenther *et al.* (2018) describe the various types of publics in these communities, emphasising rural communities and their differing cultural distances from science. These publics can be divided into two groups: on one side, literate and educated individuals who mainly reside in urban areas and frequently access and use sources of scientific information. On the other hand, those living in rural areas, who generally have lower education levels and literacy rates, express more scepticism and see fewer benefits in science and technology (S&T). A significant challenge for this second group is their lower income and infrequent use of scientific information sources, possibly due to limited access (Guenther & Weingart, 2018; Guenther *et al.*, 2018).

In many rural communities, the lack of access to the internet and computer infrastructure makes it challenging to access new knowledge and stay connected to the broader information landscape. Without reliable internet connectivity, individuals may be cut off from the wealth of information, educational resources, and online learning opportunities. This limits their ability to engage with new scientific discoveries, advancements, and developments commonly shared and disseminated through digital platforms.

Furthermore, the absence of computer infrastructure and technological resources in these communities hinders individuals from acquiring digital literacy skills and proficiency. In an increasingly digital world, where access to information and communication technologies is vital, the lack of such infrastructure creates a digital divide, deepening the disparities in knowledge and access to educational opportunities.

The presence of inadequate transportation systems, deficient road infrastructure, and unreliable internet connectivity in these communities poses significant challenges for science communication personnel to engage with them effectively. Consequently, it becomes difficult for these personnel to make the necessary journeys to these locations for public engagement activities. This situation sheds light on the methods of public engagement and highlights the unfortunate reality that, without intentional and transformative efforts towards change and inclusivity, entire communities are disproportionately left behind.

There are various efforts in South Africa to communicate science through different broadcasting and media platforms, with organisations also making strides in using

social media. However, these efforts remain insufficient when it comes to the field of astronomy. Although National Science Week receives extensive media coverage, much of that coverage tends to focus on promoting the event, serving more as public relations rather than truly communicating the science to the public. Moreover, there is limited engagement specifically related to astronomy. As a result, while many people may be aware of the event, few have the opportunity to engage meaningfully with the scientific content being presented.

This is not to undermine the commendable work done by the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI), the South African Agency for Science and Technology Advancement (SAASTA), and many other notable organisations that strive to facilitate science engagement through various platforms, as supported by the Science Engagement Strategy, specifically the strategic aim “To promote science communication that will enhance science engagement in South Africa”, which has a specific outcome of increasing media coverage of science and technology issues in South Africa (Department of Science and Technology [DST], 2015)

Significant progress and improvements have indeed been made. Social media and broadcasting hold great potential for science communication, especially in reaching marginalised communities that have access to platforms such as radio and social media (Nkoala, 2023)

Limited access to new knowledge in marginalised communities exacerbates existing inequalities and hampers the potential for public engagement in science. It restricts individuals from staying informed about scientific advancements, participating in online scientific communities, or utilising online learning platforms. This further perpetuates the gap in scientific literacy and restricts the ability of individuals in marginalised communities to engage fully and benefit from scientific knowledge.

Language barriers

The issue of language is one of the biggest barriers to public engagement with science in South Africa. This topic is quite complex, too, with political, socio-cultural, and historical implications, particularly in the context of South Africa (Nemadziva *et al.*, 2023)

South Africa is a nation with diverse people, cultures, and languages. There are eleven official languages. English is a prominent urban language in South Africa, playing a significant role in public life, media, business, and government. Furthermore, English is widely utilised as a second language and serves as a common medium of communication, particularly in urban areas and cities throughout the country. However, among a population of over 62 million South Africans, only about 8.7% speak English in their households (Statistics South Africa, n.d.). Further, more than 80% of the South African population is Black African, but only 4.4% of Black Africans speak English as a first language; using English as the primary language in any event can represent a huge barrier to access (Canfield & Menezes, 2020; Márquez & Porras, 2020). In addition, the dominant position of English in science leads to the reinforcement of one specific cultural perspective while disregarding others (Alves & Pozzebon, 2013).

Studies have demonstrated that there are advantages to conducting science engagement activities in Indigenous or local languages and with attention to cultural considerations, and this is far more inclusive. Fish *et al.* (2017) echo this point but argue that South Africa faces challenges in implementing multilingual science engagement programs due to limited capacity.

Public engagement in science faces a significant challenge regarding the use of basic English as a means of communication. However, an additional barrier arises within the field of science itself, characterised by the extensive use of specialised terminology and jargon, further complicating the understanding for the general public or non-experts. This language barrier hinders effective communication and comprehension, making it even more challenging for individuals to grasp scientific concepts and engage meaningfully with scientific information. The Cascade Outreach Model (discussed below) addresses this challenge by placing ambassadors in communities who are fluent in the local language. This allows them to translate scientific concepts into the local language, fostering better understanding. In cases where specific scientific terms do not exist in the local language, ambassadors explain or

elaborate on these concepts using culturally relevant language. This approach has proven highly effective in overcoming language barriers and facilitating meaningful engagement.

Using jargon can worsen the issue by creating a barrier that excludes an even wider group of individuals from the conversation. Jargon pertains to words or phrases specific to certain niches or industries, making it comprehensible only to a select group of specialists or participants. As a result, effective engagement with science becomes limited, as only those who know such jargon can fully understand and participate in the discourse.

The predominance of English as the primary mode of communication, teaching, and learning also contributes to cultural barriers in science. This reliance on English raises concerns about cultural marginalisation by creating a perceived separation between science and culture. Researchers such as Augare *et al.* (2017) and Biyela (2019) have highlighted this issue. The dominance of English in scientific discourse can lead to overlooking or marginalising other cultural perspectives and indigenous knowledge systems. This exclusion limits the representation of diverse worldviews and impedes the integration of local knowledge and traditions into scientific practices. As a result, the overemphasis on English in science communication can perpetuate the erasure of cultural diversity and undervalue contributions from non-Western knowledge systems. A study by Charamba (2020) highlights how language choices influence the accessibility and integration of science within local contexts and proposes translanguaging as “an alternative educational pedagogy for the multilingual science student since it acknowledges linguistic diversity, which in turn facilitates education for sustainable development”. This is the approach of the Cascade Outreach Model, as translanguaging is applied in the context of communicating astronomy with the public. While the South African government’s Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) Policy, developed by the Department of Science and Innovation, represents a progressive effort to safeguard cultural heritage (DST, 2004), challenges related to language remain prevalent – particularly in a linguistically diverse country like South Africa.

Language barriers extend beyond the realm of comprehension and extend to basic human interactions. Simple gestures like greetings or using local language phrases can significantly influence the reception and acceptance of information during public engagements. Unfortunately, science communicators or public engagement officers often overlook or underestimate the impact of these small acts, inadvertently creating barriers in their interactions with the public. Recognising and valuing the importance of such gestures can foster fruitful engagements and enhance openness to dialogue.

Cultural barriers: Representation or the lack thereof

Students from under-represented groups, such as racial and ethnic minorities, women, and individuals from low-income backgrounds, often face a lack of role models in STEM careers. Role models are crucial in inspiring and motivating individuals, particularly when they can relate to someone with similar backgrounds and experiences. Having visible role models who are “like them” can significantly impact students’ aspirations and self-belief. It helps them envision themselves pursuing and succeeding in STEM fields, breaking down stereotypes and addressing the sense of exclusion they may experience. (e.g., Shin *et al.*, 2016)

In South Africa, there remains a notable lack of diversity and transformation in science careers. It is important to acknowledge the efforts made by certain organisations to address this issue. However, it is necessary to recognise the current state of affairs that is still largely common. One significant barrier to effective science public engagement is the lack of representation among science communicators or science engagement practitioners.

The demographic representation of scientific leadership in South Africa does not accurately reflect the diversity of the population, creating challenges for young people to identify with scientists and envision themselves in scientific careers. One such example is the gender imbalance in STEM careers (United Nations, 2015), which shows that there is a significant disparity in the proportion of male and female students choosing science and engineering fields globally. The statistics reveal that more male students opt for these

disciplines than their female counterparts. Specifically, approximately one in five men graduate in engineering, while one in nine graduate in science. In contrast, only about one in twenty women graduate in engineering, and one in fourteen graduate in science (*United Nations, 2015; Malhotra, 2018*).

A large portion of science communication methods in South Africa lack cultural relevance and are unable to connect science to people and their lived experiences. This lack of representation is evident in several ways. One is that the material or resources disseminated to the general public often lack relatability. For instance, the images used frequently depict men as scientists, perpetuating the stereotype that only men can succeed in this field. Similarly, using certain terminology or exclusive language can further reinforce these stereotypes, making the information less accessible and inclusive. *Bahji et al. (2023)* explored the reasons behind excluding scientific contributions from the non-English-speaking world, particularly those from the Global South, from mainstream literature and media. They highlight that the dominance of English in science communication has significant repercussions, notably leading to a bias towards research topics that primarily interest English-speaking audiences.

An important challenge in public engagement in astronomy, particularly for learners in the Global South, is that the content in the school curriculum often tends to be based on information and perspectives primarily relevant to the Northern Hemisphere. This can create difficulties for learners in the Global South relating to the information and accurately visualising astronomical phenomena. This is because science learning is enhanced when concepts are relevant to an individual's context and culture (*Brown, 2017; Tan & Barton, 2018; Feliu-Mojer, 2022*).

Furthermore, the science communication teams themselves often lack diversity. While they may be relevant and effective in certain settings or environments, they can be irrelevant in other contexts, particularly within marginalised communities with minimal participation or engagement with science. The need for transformation and inclusivity is particularly crucial in these communities.

Lack of partnerships and collaboration among organisations and individuals working towards similar objectives

The presence of disciplinary, sectoral, and modal silos poses a significant challenge to achieving greater integration of inclusive and equitable practices. These silos refer to the divisions and boundaries that exist between different disciplines, sectors, and modes of operation, limiting collaboration and hindering the adoption of inclusive practices (*Bevan & Smith, 2020; Canfield & Menezes, 2020; Menezes et al., 2022*).

Many organisations and individuals often operate in silos, duplicating efforts and resources that could be better utilised if shared. These barriers create redundancy, duplicate efforts, and inhibit opportunities for collaboration (*Bevan et al., 2018; Menezes et al., 2022*). Overcoming this barrier requires collaborative efforts and partnerships among researchers, science engagement practitioners, and organisations with different mandates but the same target audience.

These diverse groups can combine their expertise, resources, and networks by forming partnerships to increase their impact and create meaningful change. Collaboration allows for sharing best practices, knowledge, and experiences, enabling more effective and efficient public engagement in science. It also helps to avoid duplication of efforts and ensures a more coordinated approach to reaching the target audience.

Partnerships facilitate the pooling of resources, including funding, infrastructure, and personnel, which can lead to the development of innovative and comprehensive science engagement initiatives. By working together, organisations and individuals can leverage each other's strengths and overcome individual limitations, thereby enhancing the quality and reach of their programs.

Moreover, partnerships enable a more holistic and inclusive approach to public engagement in science. Different organisations and individuals bring unique perspectives, expertise, and networks to the table, ensuring a wider range of voices and communities are involved. This diversity can lead to more culturally relevant and engaging science communication,

making science accessible and relatable to a broader audience.

It is essential to address these barriers by actively promoting diversity and representation in science communication. This involves creating materials and resources that are inclusive, relatable, and accessible to a diverse range of individuals. Additionally, science communication teams should be diverse and representative of the communities they aim to engage with, enabling effective communication and fostering meaningful connections.

By recognising and addressing these challenges and designing more culturally sensitive public engagement methods, individuals and organisations can contribute to making science more meaningful to various audiences. This approach aims to counter harmful stereotypes and foster a sense of agency and belonging, particularly among historically excluded populations. (*Davies et al., 2019; Baxter, 2022; Feliu-Mojer, 2022*)

The Cascade Outreach Model

The Cascade Outreach Model is "an outreach framework designed to promote diversity, inclusivity, and relatable role-modelling while training a new generation of scientists in communication and leadership skills" (*IDIA, 2025*). Pioneered by the late Professor Carolina Ödman-Govender, this innovative framework was developed to provide a structured approach to fostering diversity and inclusivity in science outreach while also empowering scientist-communicators. Professor Ödman-Govender's vision centred on addressing gaps in science communication by equipping scientists with the necessary skills to engage effectively with communities, particularly those traditionally underrepresented in STEM fields.

The model emphasises creating relatable role models to inspire the next generation of scientists. It operates on a cascading effect, similar to the concept of near-peer mentoring, where trained communicators pass on their knowledge and enthusiasm to others, who then continue the cycle. Crucially, the model ensures that scientist-communicators share

their knowledge and are empowered through the process. They gain valuable communication and teaching skills, as well as increased confidence to navigate both professional and public-facing roles.

The unique focus on the personal and professional challenges that scientists face, especially those related to communication, is rarely the focus of the goals and objectives set for outreach projects. However, the Cascade Outreach Model acknowledges these concerns and prioritises equipping scientists with the tools needed to overcome them while also attempting to mitigate the challenges and barriers with public engagement listed above.

The aim of the Cascade Outreach Model

The primary aims of the model are to:

- Promote diversity and inclusivity by increasing the number of relatable role models from diverse backgrounds.
- Facilitate relatable role modelling by engaging young scientists to serve as role models for the next generation, making science more accessible and inspiring.
- Provide training in communication and leadership, thus equipping young scientists with valuable skills both in and outside academia.
- Reduce the burden on minority scientists by spreading outreach responsibilities more evenly and sustainably, preventing the over-reliance on a few individuals from underrepresented groups.
- Create sustained impact by enabling continuous interactions and follow-up rather than relying on one-off events.

Why the Cascade Model?

The Cascade Model is considered a good fit for public engagement programmes because it emphasises inclusion and relatability rather than prestige. By prioritising role models relatable to the audience rather than celebrated figures within the scientific community, the model makes science careers appear achievable and accessible to young people. Furthermore, it promotes sustainability and continuous engagement by encouraging ongoing interactions that have a more profound and lasting influence on young people's career choices and scientific interests compared to one-off events. The model also leverages the natural enthusiasm of young scientists, often from

modest and relatable backgrounds, who are genuinely motivated to give back to their communities. It addresses challenges such as imposter syndrome, language barriers, and a lack of career awareness – particularly relevant issues in contexts like South Africa. Additionally, the Cascade Model fosters a supportive ecosystem where young scientists receive mentorship, develop leadership skills, and inspire others, creating a multiplier effect that amplifies its impact.

Key benefits of the Cascade Outreach Model

Enhanced communication and teaching skills

A critical need for improving scientific literacy is to increase the number of scientists actively engaged in public communication. Many scientists, however, encounter barriers to participating in outreach, with a lack of formal training in science communication being one of the most commonly cited reasons (Woitowich *et al.*, 2022; Swords *et al.*, 2023).

The Cascade Outreach Model addresses this issue by providing scientists with opportunities to refine their communication skills. By participating in outreach, scientists develop their ability to explain complex concepts in an accessible way to various audiences. This experience also builds their confidence, making them more effective communicators in academic and public settings.

An evaluation was conducted with the team leads after the event to gather feedback on the activities, including any challenges faced, achievements reached, and recommendations for improvement. To quote one of the ambassadors who reflected on their experience:

“It was my first time doing public speaking, and I learnt a lot from all of my teammates, more specifically from Karabo, in terms of public speaking when engaging with kids. And thanks again for the opportunity... For me, the trip revived something in me that I just noticed I missed doing – talking about what I love to the young minds. I am, therefore, super-duper grateful for the opportunity I was given to be part of the event. I am open and motivated for the next one.”

The Model allows scientists to gain teaching experience in addition to communication

skills. By leading workshops, giving presentations, and conducting educational activities, they become more adept at engaging learners of different backgrounds and learning styles. This dual focus on communication and teaching equips scientist-communicators with valuable skills they can use throughout their careers in academia and beyond.

Overcoming language barriers

One of the Model's most significant contributions to inclusivity is its ability to overcome language barriers. Language can be a significant obstacle in many outreach efforts, especially in regions with diverse linguistic backgrounds. The Cascade Outreach Model addresses this by recruiting fluent ambassadors in the local languages of the communities they serve. By delivering astronomy and other scientific content in languages that are accessible to the audience, the model makes science more relatable and reduces the sense of alienation that can occur when learning about complex topics in unfamiliar languages.

This approach enhances understanding and fosters a deeper connection between the audience and the subject matter. When people can engage with science in their own language, they are more likely to see it as relevant to their lives and communities, leading to greater interest and participation.

Increasing awareness of opportunities

The Model also plays a critical role in raising awareness of educational and career opportunities in STEM fields, particularly for young people in underrepresented communities. By providing relatable role models – scientists from similar backgrounds and have faced similar challenges – the Model inspires students to see themselves in those roles. The outreach activities highlight pathways to STEM careers, including the steps necessary to pursue them, such as education, mentorship, and community involvement.

By raising awareness of these opportunities, the Model helps to bridge the gap between aspiration and achievement, encouraging more students from diverse backgrounds to consider careers in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

Promoting transformation and diversity

A central goal of the Cascade Outreach Model is to promote transformation and

diversity within the scientific community. By intentionally focusing on outreach to underrepresented groups, the model creates a more inclusive and equitable field of science. The involvement of scientists from diverse backgrounds in outreach activities benefits the communities they serve and helps shift the demographics of those actively involved in science.

The cascading effect of the model encourages participants to develop a sense of responsibility and leadership. The scientist-communicators trained through this model can become ambassadors for diversity and inclusion in their outreach activities and professional careers. By serving as relatable role models and effectively communicating astronomy and STEM to learners, the model helps increase the likelihood of more students pursuing careers in science and astronomy.

Implementation of the Cascade Outreach Model During National Science Week

The National Science Week

National Science Week (NSW) is a significant event in South Africa aimed at promoting science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) across the country. A project initiated by the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI) and coordinated by the National Research Foundation's South African Agency for Science and Technology Advancement (NRF-SAASTA), the National Science Week serves as a platform to inspire and engage communities, especially the youth, in various scientific fields, fostering interest and potential career paths in STEM. As stated on the SAASTA website, "this annual event aims to close the gap between society and science, since science has an impact on every aspect of people's lives" (SAASTA, *n.d*). Since it was established in 2000, NSW has achieved national reach.

Astronomy engagement during the National Science Week (NSW)

Although the Cascade Outreach Model can be applied to communicate any scientific discipline, in this context, it was employed to facilitate astronomy outreach and engagement with the South African community during National Science Week. The communicators comprised

undergraduate and postgraduate astronomy students from institutions across the country.

Despite the participation of numerous organisations in National Science Week, astronomy is typically represented by only a few entities, including the South African Astronomical Observatory, the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory, the Iziko Planetarium, the Boyden Observatory, and the Naval Hill Planetarium. Consequently, astronomy's reach remains limited, contributing to a general lack of public awareness about it, its infrastructure, and the associated opportunities within South Africa.

The African Astronomical Society (AfAS) and the BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network (BITDN) project focused their outreach efforts during National Science Week on bringing astronomy to a diverse array of communities, with particular emphasis on underserved and rural areas. To increase awareness and interest in astronomy, these activities encompassed stargazing events, role modelling sessions, hands-on activities, and public demonstrations and presentations.

With funding secured and a team of passionate student ambassadors, the initiative aimed to inspire and engage diverse communities, especially in underserved rural areas. This multi-step programme involved meticulous planning, from ambassador selection and training to navigating travel logistics, culminating in

impactful engagements during NSW. The programme's implementation was rolled out in several phases, detailed below.

Step 1: Securing funding

South Africa celebrates National Science Week annually in July. The African Astronomical Society Outreach and Education Committee and the BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network (BITDN) project team applied for funding to conduct astronomy engagement activities across six provinces during National Science Week. The application was successful, and the necessary funds were secured.

Step 2: Call for ambassadors

After securing funds, the committee issued a call for ambassadors to participate in the outreach activities. This call was distributed nationally through various mailing lists, universities, and key astronomy partners, such as the South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO) and the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO). The response exceeded expectations, reflecting the strong interest among students in engaging in community outreach and empowerment initiatives. The opportunity to return to and serve their communities particularly resonated with many students.

Step 3: Selection and allocation of ambassadors

The selection process considered candidates' availability, travel distances, and potential costs. Once finalised, ambassadors were chosen and briefed on their roles. Ambassador agreements were drafted and signed to clearly outline both parties' expectations, roles, and responsibilities, ensuring a mutual understanding of the engagement. The selection process prioritised the objectives of the Cascade Model, particularly the emphasis on relatability. Factors such as location and language were carefully considered to ensure that each ambassador could serve in a community where they would be most beneficial.

Step 4: Ambassador training

Before National Science Week, an online training and briefing session was conducted for the ambassadors. This session covered basic science engagement techniques, expectations,

and guidelines for outreach activities. While the training provided a foundational understanding, the team recognised that this area could be improved in future iterations. Ambassadors were also provided basic resources to aid their preparations for the engagements.

The science engagement techniques within the Cascade Outreach Model were centred on establishing meaningful connections with the audience. One key approach was using learners' home languages in each region, which enhanced the model's effectiveness by fostering relatability. Many ambassadors were fluent in the local languages and shared similar backgrounds and life experiences with the communities they served. This enabled them to use culturally relevant examples and analogies that resonated with the learners, facilitating easier comprehension and engagement. Establishing such emotional connections is crucial for effective outreach.

Furthermore, the diversity of the ambassador teams allowed learners to identify with role models from their own communities, increasing the impact of the engagement. The training sessions highlighted the importance of role modelling, where ambassadors shared their personal career journeys and pathways to success. By incorporating elements of storytelling, the ambassadors were able to inspire and motivate learners, making the outreach more impactful and meaningful. Through storytelling, science communicators can spark interest and make science more relevant by connecting the audience and the subject matter. Storytelling does more than just present facts; it builds emotional connections between scientists and the public (Joubert *et al.*, 2019).

Storytelling can be a more effective way of communicating science, especially basic sciences. As Martinez-Conde & Macknik (2017) note, "science breakthroughs that resonate with non-experts, despite having no immediate application, do so because they captivate our imagination and evoke emotion."

Step 5: Engagement with local education districts

Engagement with local education districts and community leaders was crucial for

the success of the outreach activities. Leading up to NSW, the team worked diligently to obtain the necessary permissions to access schools and communities. This process varied significantly across provinces and required substantial time and effort. However, sufficient support was secured after persistent engagement, and plans were finalised for the outreach activities.

Step 6: Travel logistics

Coordinating travel logistics presented one of the most significant challenges of the project. Ensuring cost-effective arrangements for accommodations, vehicles, and flights was complex, particularly for teams travelling to remote communities. While some ambassadors were already based in the target areas, reducing costs, others faced higher expenses due to the remoteness of their assigned locations.

As detailed earlier, reaching rural and remote communities posed significant challenges. Unlike urban areas, which are well-connected and resource-rich, rural communities often lack adequate infrastructure, making access difficult and costly. This situation required additional effort and resources to overcome logistical barriers and successfully engage with these underserved areas.

Step 7: Implementation

During National Science Week, teams were deployed to districts in six provinces: Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, Western Cape, Free State, Limpopo, and Mpumalanga. The outreach activities included engaging

presentations, role modelling sessions, practical demonstrations, and visits to multiple schools, all centred around astronomy. Ambassadors, who often had personal ties to the communities they served, could communicate in the local languages and share relatable life experiences, making the engagements more impactful. The activities were adapted on the spot to suit the specific needs of each community and school, ensuring that the outreach was both effective and engaging for all participants.

Results and impact

The project significantly impacted more than 6,900 learners and 200 teachers during National Science Week, particularly in remote and underserved communities across South Africa. These communities, often isolated geographically and with limited access to scientific resources, were specifically targeted to bridge the gap in astronomy education. By focusing on learners in townships and remote areas, the initiative not only introduced them to fundamental concepts in astronomy but also provided a unique opportunity for these students to engage with individuals who look like them and share similar backgrounds and life experiences. This personalised approach proved highly effective, allowing learners to see themselves reflected in astronomy, making the subject matter more relatable and accessible.

The presence of young astronomers from similar communities served as powerful role models, transforming astronomy from an abstract and distant concept into a tangible

and achievable reality. The learners were inspired to dream bigger and believe in their academic and scientific potential. This shift in perception is crucial for fostering long-term interest in STEM fields, particularly in historically underrepresented communities in science.

In addition to its impact on learners, the project also provided invaluable experience for the 36 postgraduate students who served as science communicators and role models. These students gained hands-on experience in science communication and outreach, essential skills for developing socially conscious scientists. By participating in this initiative, the young astronomers enhanced their ability to communicate complex scientific ideas to a general audience. They deepened their understanding of the social responsibilities of their roles as scientists.

The project's success in engaging over 6,000 learners and 200 teachers across six provinces – through visits to two or three schools per day in each province – highlights the effectiveness of the Cascade Outreach Model in promoting science awareness. This model facilitated the creation of a supportive network of science communicators better equipped to continue their outreach efforts, fostering ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange within the scientific community and beyond.

Furthermore, the initiative's impact extended beyond the immediate engagement, contributing to increased public awareness of astronomy and its relevance to everyday life. By nurturing a new generation of socially aware scientists skilled in science communication, the project has laid the groundwork for continued efforts to inspire

and educate future generations about the wonders of astronomy. The collective dedication of all participants – from the funding bodies to the postgraduate students – underscores the power of collaboration in bringing the marvels of astronomy to communities under the shared skies of Africa. While further research is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of this model thoroughly, feedback from schools and ambassadors indicates it was successful. However, improvements are needed in areas such as training and implementation. Despite this, the Model shows promise for achieving meaningful and impactful engagement.

Challenges and lessons learned from the project implementation

The project faced several challenges during its implementation, offering valuable lessons for future efforts:

High travel costs

One of the main challenges was the expense associated with travel, particularly to remote areas. A key lesson is to reduce these costs by localising outreach efforts and utilising ambassadors already based in or near the target communities, except in special cases where travel to remote areas is essential.

Time-consuming logistics

Managing travel arrangements and logistics was a significant time investment. A lesson learned is to delegate this responsibility to the ambassadors, empowering them to handle their travel and scheduling, thus streamlining the process.

The need for more comprehensive training

A more structured and thorough training programme for ambassadors is essential. This would build their confidence, especially for those with little to no experience, and equip them with practical science communication and outreach skills. This training would benefit the project and provide ambassadors with transferable skills that could be applied in their future endeavours.

Next steps: Call for seed grants to implement the Cascade Outreach Model

Despite the challenges, the project was a notable success, motivating the committee to continue and expand the Cascade Outreach Model across Africa. To facilitate this expansion, a call for Cascade Outreach Seed Grants was released. These grants are designed to support students and young professionals in astronomy, astrophysics, or other STEM disciplines throughout Africa.

Eligible applicants were required to reside in Africa, and the prospective funding covered travel expenses within their home countries. Additionally, applicants needed to demonstrate reliable affiliations and provide traceable references. The response was overwhelming, with over 70 applications from more than 24 African countries.

Successful applicants will receive science communication training, providing an opportunity and platform for sharing knowledge and best practices. This decentralised approach shifts the central committee's responsibility for logistics and

stakeholder engagement to a broader network of ambassadors. By distributing these responsibilities, the initiative can reach a wider audience across Africa, as more ambassadors will conduct outreach activities in various regions.

Moreover, this strategy significantly reduces costs, particularly in travel, as long-distance travel is minimised, except in special cases where teams must reach remote communities. This approach enhances the project's sustainability and ensures a broader and more efficient dissemination of astronomy knowledge across the continent.

The 2023 National Science Week Cascade Project has demonstrated its potential as a catalyst for sustained community impact. Many ambassadors who participated in the initiative have since applied for seed grants, and several have successfully secured funding. These grants have empowered them to independently build upon the lessons and skills gained during the project, enabling them to make meaningful contributions to their communities. Notably, these ambassadors have also shared their experiences and insights with newer participants, fostering a culture of mentorship and growth.

A significant highlight of their contributions was during the International Astronomical Union's General Assembly (IAU-GA), hosted in Cape Town, South Africa, in August 2024. Their collaborative efforts during this global event were pivotal in outreach, education, and community engagement, reaching over 28,000 school learners and more than 3,800 members of the public (Kubheka & Macfarlane, 2024). This collective impact underscores the effectiveness of the Cascade Model in creating a sustainable cycle of knowledge-sharing and community enrichment.

Conclusion

Public engagement with science in South Africa is marked by complex and deeply rooted challenges encompassing socio-economic, educational, cultural, and infrastructural barriers. Ongoing inequalities, especially within the education system, continue to restrict access to scientific knowledge and digital resources, most notably in rural and underserved communities. Language barriers and the

limited representation of diverse groups in astronomy and general STEM fields further complicate efforts to fully engage the public in scientific endeavours.

The Cascade Outreach Model has emerged as a promising approach to contribute to the many existing efforts that seek to address these challenges, as demonstrated during its implementation in National Science Week. By prioritising diversity, inclusivity, and relatable role models, the model has successfully empowered learners and ambassadors, fostering meaningful science communication and leadership.

The project reached over 6,900 learners and 200 teachers across six provinces, emphasising engagement with rural areas. Participating ambassadors, 36 in total, reported growth in science communication and leadership skills, while learners expressed increased curiosity and inspiration to pursue STEM careers. Using local languages and culturally relevant narratives further enhanced comprehension and relatability, ensuring the initiative resonated with diverse audiences.

To build on this success, future efforts aim to focus on comprehensive training for ambassadors, expanded seed grant programs to empower independent outreach, longitudinal studies to assess long-term impacts on learners' aspirations and scientific literacy, and the ambassador's science communication and leadership skills. Investigating the Model's scalability to

other African contexts and its adaptability to various scientific disciplines could further extend its reach. Strengthening partnerships with local education districts, science organisations, and community leaders will also ensure continued support and shared resources.

We can bridge the gap between science and society by emphasising inclusivity, diversity, and the cultivation of local leadership in science outreach. Continued refinements and sustained research will be essential to maximising the Model's impact,

positioning science as a powerful catalyst for empowerment and development across all communities.

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Biography

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